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Abstract

Fishponds are interesting freshwater systems where natural and anthropogenic processes interact, mirroring the biogeochemical cycles found in natural wetlands, and providing a wide range of ecosystem services (ES) such as provisioning, regulating and cultural services. The investigation of a wide range of services provided by fishponds, both in terms of biophysical and monetary accounting, remains critical to ensure the cost-effective provision of ES. Therefore, the aim of our study was to carry out a model-based assessment of the ecosystem services (ES) provided by fishpond aquaculture and, furthermore, to perform a monetary valuation of these ecosystem services. The work was carried out in two steps: first, a biophysical process model of the pond food web and associated reed vegetation was developed. The unified elements of Programmable Process Structures (PPS) are used to analyse the underlying processes (physical, chemical, biological, ecological, technological, and managerial) and to determine the effects of management interventions on the environmental interactions of the fishpond agroecosystem. It is also discussed how the calculated quantitative environmental interactions can be used for a more rigorous assessment of ecosystem services (ES). It is concluded that many categories of ES (such as provisioning and regulatory services) can be derived directly from the quantitative environmental interactions. Other categories, such as habitat maintenance for biodiversity and cultural services, can be derived by combining the simulated quantitative data with expert-defined qualitative rules. In the next step, a monetary valuation of these ecosystem services was carried out using various methods such as replacement cost method, market price method, application of social cost of carbon etc. to determine the value in economic terms. The results of this study will be helpful in the development of programmes for the protection and sustainable management of pond aquaculture systems.

Keywords: Fishponds; Aquaculture; Ecosystem Services; Process Modelling; Monetary Valuation

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1. Introduction

Achieving food and nutrition security involves aquaculture in a big way. According to FAO statistics, in 2022, aquaculture accounted for 59% (130.9 million tons) of the total global fisheries and aquaculture production of 223.2 million tons, and this share of aquatic animal production is projected to increase by 10% by 2032 (FAO 2024). On an average 20% of all freshwater production in the European Union (EU), pond carp farming is the second largest sub-segment of freshwater aquaculture after cold-water flow-through systems. An estimated 360,000 hectares make up all the fishponds in the EU, most of which are in areas of natural importance (EUMOFA 2021). Fishpond production is dominant in Central European countries such as the Czech Republic, Poland, Hungary, and Germany and contribute to almost 80 % of the total carp production in the EU. Hungary is the third largest producer of common carp in Europe, with an annual production of 21,184 tons and an operating area of 25,937 hectares in 2021 (Kiss 2022). The traditional and most common form of aquaculture in Hungary is fish production in earthen ponds, mainly round dam ponds (also called embankment ponds) in the Hungarian Great Plain. Fishpond systems in these regions are mainly managed using extensive or semi-intensive methods with relatively low yields.

Pond aquaculture systems function as integrated ecological systems where natural and human-induced processes work together, mirroring the biogeochemical cycles found in natural wetlands and deliver a wide range of ecosystem services (ES) such as provisioning, regulating and cultural services. The diverse habitat of fishponds, including open water, dry pond areas, and vegetation patches, promotes multiple materials and non-material benefits to society. Various studies interpret these benefits as provisioning, regulating, and cultural ES provided by freshwater ecosystems (Rey-Valette et al. 2024, Turkowski & Lirski 2011). The utility value of the fishponds in monetary terms has also been assessed in other studies. For example, Turkowski & Lirski (2010), estimated that for fishponds in Poland, this value could reach an average of 52,857 Euros per hectare. The ES conceptual framework and ES typologies explored by Willot et al. (2019) to complement the ecosystem approach to aquaculture (EAA) also identified a list of 10 provisioning, 20 regulation and maintenance, and 11 cultural ES for aquatic ecosystems including fishponds. In addition to the fish harvested as a main product from the ponds, the appropriate density of stocked carp helps to control the dominance of planktonic organic matter, thus contributing to the stability of the system and the generation of multiple ES (Holmlund & Hammer 1999). The harvested biomass from the reed beds surrounding the fishponds serves multiple purposes, including roof thatching material, insulation material, contributions to the paper and pulp industry, utilization as fodder and fertilizer, and as a renewable energy source (Köbbing et al. 2013). Although production services from fishponds are deemed more popular, the support of the system to conserve biodiversity holds significant value (Turkowski 2021). Aquatic space along with the reed beds supports the waterfowl by providing them with nesting, resting, and feeding habitats. Depending on their water supply, ponds can turn into reedy areas or shrubby meadows without aquaculture practices or any other kind of active management, resulting in losses of both biodiversity and ES (Broyer et al. 2016). The EU has also outlined how aquaculture can be integrated into Natura 2000 to revitalize degraded wetlands and provide habitats for biodiversity. Important regulating and maintaining services of the fishpond include the ability to sequester and capture carbon in the standing water and associated vegetation (Ahmed et al. 2017, Farrant et al. 2021); to regulate the microclimate by influencing temperature and humidity (Gao et al. 2020) and to improve the quality of the water used in the fish farming process by absorbing contaminants (Kerepeczki et al. 2011). Managed fishponds have a lower environmental impact than other food sectors in Europe, as the economic as well as environmental benefits outweigh the nutrient footprint contributed by the cereal-based feed used in ponds (Roy et al. 2020). In addition, their ability to store surplus/excess/runoff water throughout the year accounts for another passive ecosystem service (Lhotský 2010). Since the fishpond landscapes have historically been important sources of livelihood, a significant portion of the population's cultural history and sense of place values are vital to their well-being. Opportunities for

recreation and ecotourism activities such as bird watching, hiking, biking, angling, hunting, etc. in the fishponds contribute to improving the physical and mental well-being of society (Xu et al. 2020). Furthermore, fishponds represent an extremely significant part of the rich natural and cultural history of various fish farming communities. Many of the ponds under fish-production have a protected status or in other cases their proximity to National Parks and other sizable protected areas, where nature trails and information centres are utilized to teach the public about nature and natural processes, address the educational components of fishponds. These complex systems are also interesting sites for studying various scientific issues and carrying out monitoring activities (Roebeling et al. 2016). On the other hand, the aesthetics of fishponds is seen as an inspiration source in historical as well as present documentation e.g., books, paintings, drawings, stories, etc. (Turkowski & Lirski 2011). Palásti et al. (2020) highlighted the lack of practical information on the diverse water-related ES in fishponds compared to other ecosystems, while their findings substantiate theoretical claims and provided valuable guidance for future land-use planning aimed at improving sustainability in multifunctional fishpond systems. Thus, the investigation of a wide range of pond management activities remains critical to ensure the cost-effective provision of ES (Landuyt et al. 2014).

It is essential to focus not only on individual services or features for management, but also to consider the relationships between the different components of human-environment systems (Kandziora et al. 2013). These relationships can be interpreted as “ecological indicators” as a result of many inter- and intra-system environmental interactions. To better understand the complex realities of agroecosystems and to predict future ecosystem responses, it is particularly important to have a mechanistic understanding of ecosystem functions and possible linkages between ecosystem functions and services (Calder et al. 2009). In this regard quantitative modelling plays an important role in ES assessment. As different agro-environmental systems consist of interlinked sub-systems, the models used for assessment need to be tailored according to their respective specifications. Based on other reviews conducted by Busch et al. (2012); Martnez-Harms & Balvanera (2012) and Petz (2014), ES mapping approaches can be broadly classified into statistical/empirical models, biophysical models, proxy-based methods, GIS-based methods, and qualitative techniques. Using the above methodologies, several tools have been developed for integrating ES into public and private sector decision-making processes. Examples of the two most widely used tools for quantifying ES at the landscape scale are Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs (InVEST) (Natural Capital Project 2024) and Artificial Intelligence for Ecosystem Services (ARIES) (Villa et al. 2014). However, because decision-makers often don't have much familiarity with these complex models, scientists usually must face the crucial hurdle of getting stakeholders on board. Scalability of these models are also a big concern, as certain generalized models may work very well at the national to regional level, but they can't consider local influences on the supply, demand, and value of ES (Bagstad et al. 2013, Troy & Wilson 2006).

In the context of the aforementioned justification, the aim of this work is to carry out a model-based assessment of the ecosystem services (ES) provided by fishpond aquaculture and, furthermore, to perform a monetary valuation of the ES. This study was carried out in two steps: first, the biophysical model for fishpond aquaculture was developed in order to adequately quantify ES and identify ES indicators. In the next step, a monetary valuation was carried out to determine the economic value of the ecosystem services provided by fishpond aquaculture.

2. Development of pond aquaculture model

To accurately quantify the environmental interactions responsible for the provision of ecosystem services, we started by building a process-based fishpond model.

Typical Hungarian Pond aquaculture systems served as inspiration for the model. The general components of an artificial round dam pond are included in the model development, which is not site-specific and is shown in Fig. 1. These ponds range in depth from 1 to 1.3 metres and the water management strategy of the fish farm is based on a targeted supply from rivers or artificial irrigation canals. The inner and outer pond boundaries are surrounded by a mosaic of littoral reed patches that can cover 20-25% of the pond surface. These patches consist mainly of *Phragmites* and *Typha* species and vary in size, height, and density (Sharma et al., 2023).

Figure 1. (a) Typical structure of fishponds in Hungary, (b) Field photo showing the placement of reeds in and around fishponds

As a general framework, the newly consolidated version of the PPS (Varga & Csukas, 2024) has been used for the automated generation and execution of the underlying unified, complex process models of medium complexity. The antecedent methods and applications started originally from (chemical) process engineering. Recently, with the emerging need for quantitative, dynamic, model-based analysis in the field of complex agricultural, aquacultural and environmental processes PPS shifted in this direction. PPS models consider non-linear causal transformations and transportations related to the characteristic physical, chemical, biological, ecological, technological, and managerial processes, governed by conservation laws and rules. PPS provides unified solutions for the implementation and coupled execution of different unified sub-models by generating them from one-one generally usable state and transition meta-prototypes. During the execution, the actual state and transition elements are computed by the programs of their associated state or transition prototypes. The communication between the state and transition elements is solved by uniform connections, while the generated model is executed by a general-purpose kernel program. PPS is implemented in the declarative, logical language of SWI-Prolog.

The first part of this work focused on the improvement of the reusability aspect of a previously published reference biophysical fishpond model (Varga et al., 2020) to incorporate the characteristics of a wider range of differently managed fishponds. A reference model was subjected to a stepwise improvement using measured data, progressing from simpler (“reduced”) cases utilizing the natural food web to more complex (“extended”) cases with feeding, manuring and inorganic-fertilizer input. The reference model considered was built as a component of the ClimeFish project's Decision Support System (DSS) for

assessing the effects of climate change in fishpond aquaculture. Although the reference model provided robust simulations, it had some model-related limitations. For example, the model was only partially validated, as experimental data for initial values of various food web components could only be obtained from the literature. Certain additional factors, such as the high fertilization rate or input of inorganic fertilizer - its dry matter, nitrogen and phosphorus content were also not considered. As the detritus levels in this pond model were restricted to a narrow range due to the low fertilization rate, the reference model could not account for the large sedimentation and resuspension events. Other data-related limitations included the lack of site-specific solar radiation and humidity data sets, so only estimated values from other Hungarian data sets were used.

A stepwise approach was used to develop, refine, and validate the reference model. For this improvement, data were collected from the pilot experiments conducted in two ponds (i.e., CS6, CS7) in 2021 and three ponds (i.e., CS2, CS3, CS6) in 2022 at HAKI AKI MATE (Szarvas). These ponds were sampled for chlorophyll-a, dissolved oxygen, temperature, zooplankton, feed, and fertilizer inputs, stocked and harvested fish. Site-specific meteorological data were also collected. The reference model was used to develop a computational model for pilot case studies, termed a “reduced model” (2021CS6) describing extensive fish production with low stocking rates and no external nutrient supply, and an “extended model” (2022CS6 and 2022CS2) describing intensive fish production with higher nutrient supply, with manure and optional inorganic fertilizer. A third case was also developed for food web extension, where model functionalities were further extended to consider groups of cyanobacteria and eukaryotes instead of a single state variable of phytoplankton by creating a “hypothetically extended model”. A continuous, iterative process was carried out to improve the parameters and specifics of the model. Finally, the refined model underwent several rounds of testing, improvement and validation calculations using data from two further pilot instances (2021CS7 and 2022CS3).

For additional validation of the improved model and to account for sampling and measurement errors, we used data from an additional set of experiments conducted during the ARRAINA (Advanced Research Initiatives for Nutrition and Aquaculture) project in 2014 at MATE AKI HAKI, Szarvas. Parallel experiments were conducted in three pair of ponds (2+2+2) to test alternative diet types (plant, fish oil and vegetable oil based). Finally, the improved fishpond model was tested for scale-up to a large production pond with very limited data from the site. Data on pond area, stocked and harvested fish biomass, feed and manure from a fish farm site in Biharugra (Hungary) were used for this up-scaling process. The meteorological conditions and some other missing data were adapted from the pilot experiments. All other model parameters and program prototypes remained consistent with the previously validated model.

The raw measurement data for experiments conducted in 2021, 2022 & 2014 fishponds, can be found in “Measured_Data” folder of the Mendeley database (Sharma et al., 2024a).

The improvement of the fishpond model led to a deeper understanding of pond food web components model components and their links with environmental and managerial factors. The Fig. 2 represent the different components of the refined fishpond model and their associations. Further aspects of model development, simulation results and validation can be referred from Sharma et al., 2024b.

Figure 2. Investigated fishpond model components

Fishpond processes are highly interactive with the surrounding environment, particularly the adjacent reed vegetation. To account for the wide range of environmental interactions associated with fishpond agroecosystem, a model is required that can consider the holistic processes and functions associated with the pond food web and reed vegetation. Inspired by a real fishpond ecosystem, the above improved fishpond model was extended to include the subsystems of reed vegetation (mainly monospecific strands of *Phragmites australis*) inside and on the terrestrial part of the ponds.

To construct the individual reed model, a medium complexity stoichiometric plant growth model developed by Varga, 2022 was modified based on specific knowledge of *Phragmites australis* growth characteristics and phenology from literature sources and other modelling studies such as Asaeda & Karunaratne, 2000. Based on information from literature and previous modelling studies the total biomass of the individual reed plant was divided into above-ground organs (stems, leaves and products - here referred to as panicles) and below-ground organs (rhizomes and roots). In addition, specific information on the different phenological phases, the proportion of each plant part in each growth phase, the respiration rate of each plant part and the density of shoots were incorporated into the plant model. Differences in phenological characteristics and other parameters from published literature references were also noted and were further refined through model calibration.

In the present modelling approach, stoichiometric principles have been used, to consider conservation measures in dynamic modelling. With a focus on C, H, O, N and P atoms, the state-representing elements in the fishpond model (e.g., food web elements, feed, fertilizer, inflow water, pond water), in the reed plant model (i.e., for each plant part - leaves, stems, roots, rhizomes and panicles) and in the other environmental components (e.g., soil layers and atmosphere) were extended with respective stoichiometric compositions. The reed model accounts for stoichiometric variation both within and between phenological periods. For pond food web elements, the differences in stoichiometric composition between the stoichiometric input of predators and prey were calculated. Excretion incorporated this difference in the detritus, which had a dynamic stoichiometric profile. In addition,

moisture content was also considered for each plant part of the pond food web, as it plays an important role in the overall push and pull logistics in plants and material flows between different compartments (both vertically and horizontally).

As a result, a simplified conceptual model of fishpond aquaculture system was developed. Fig 3. shows the visualization of different compartments and their connections in the pond aquaculture system.

Figure 3. Conceptual model of the fishpond-reed coupled model

The main compartments considered in the model are: [pond] containing fish, food-web, and reed vegetation; [land_reed] consisting of land with reeds around the pond; [groundlayer] - the soil beneath the pond and land; [atmosphere] representing the air and meteorological conditions; and [env] for input and output material storage outside the model's scope. The horizontal movement of the water and nutrient is based on the hydraulic and nutrient gradient.

For the reed related component, a refined plant growth model of *Phragmites australis* model was developed based on an existing crop growth model prepared by Varga (2022). Further development and modification were performed based on specific knowledge of reed growth characteristics and phenology of *Phragmites australis*. Data from various literature sources (Asaeda & Karunaratne 2000; Soetaert et al. 2004) was used for its approximate validation.

In the coupled model structure pond food web and reed, the actual state elements in these compartments represent the corresponding sets of extensive quantities and input signals as well as the calculated intensive quantities (concentrations) and output signals (e.g., state_species, state_materials, state_meteo,

state_envoutstorage etc). The actual transition elements inside or between these compartments represents the modelled transport and transformation processes, as well as rules (e.g., trans_evapotranspiration, trans_t_carp, trans_material_decomp, trans_water_balance etc). Further details related to the structure, processes and functionality of the coupled pond and reed model is presented in Sharma et al., 2025a & 2025b.

3. Using fishpond model to analyse environmental interactions

The coupled fishpond reed model was set up for a typical Hungarian round-dam fishpond system, with an area of 10 ha (400 x 250 m) and a nominal water depth of 1.3 m. The start date for the model was set to 1st February, to coincide with the filling of the pond. According to practical experiences, it was assumed that the pond had an initial volume of water, i.e., 10,000 m³, and was filled over 10 days to reach a nominal volume of 130,000 m³. Once the fish have been harvested, the water is released continuously for 20 days at the end of the season at a rate of 6500 m³ per day, until it reaches 0.1 m.

The stocking density reflects the general semi-intensive fishpond practices observed in the region and was set at 300 kg/ha. Based on local weather conditions, the production season is assumed to run from 1 April to 31 October each year. The feeding strategy involved calculating the supplied amount of feed according to the actual mass of fish. This was incorporated in the model based on the following rules: if the weight of the carp is less than 1 kg, the amount of feed given per day is 4% of the fish biomass; if the weight of the carp is between 1 and 1.5 kg, the amount of feed given per day is 3.5% of the fish biomass & if the weight of the carp is more than 1.5 kg, the amount of feed given per day is 3% of the fish biomass.

Regarding the fertilizing strategy, 1 t/ha of cattle manure was supplied to the pond on 3 February, prior to filling, followed by subsequent applications of 0.5 t/ha on 1 June, 1 July, and 1 August, thus in total 2.5 t/ha input in a season. The detailed input and output data of the baseline model can be found in the Mendeley database (Sharma et al., 2025a).

Meteorological data from the HuClim database by HungaroMet, including air temperature, wind speed, precipitation, and solar radiation from 2017 to 2021 for a fishpond in the Southern Great Plains were used for simulations. However, when the model is reused, site-specific meteorological data must be applied.

Terrestrial reed covers half of the pond perimeter in a 20 m wide band (650 m x 20 m) and 20% of the pond surface is also covered by reed. Reed growth is assumed between 28 February and 31 August, each year. In this baseline case, 75% of the above ground parts of the reed in the pond and 50 % of terrestrial reed is cut in early January and the cut reed remains in the system. Typically, 50% of the terrestrial reed biomass is always left untouched to maintain the habitat for biodiversity.

The coupled model was applied to this case and five-year simulations were run continuously between production seasons to also account for the processes and interactions occurring in between seasons. The model simulations of different environmental interactions associated with the fishpond reed agroecosystem show that, starting from some arbitrary initial conditions in the first year, the simulations of different environmental interactions (responsible for delivering various ES) reach a trend during the five-year simulation. Some examples of model-based simulations are presented in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Model simulations for (a) Sediment accumulation at the pond bottom over the period of five years; (b) side flows of nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) between the upper soil layer and the pond compartment; (c) rate of uptake of nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) by reed from the soil and from pond water; (d) water exchange between soil and atmosphere, between reeds and atmosphere, and between pond water and atmosphere; (e) rate of CO₂ sequestration and emission by reed vegetation and soil & (f) rate of O₂ produced by reed vegetation and soil

4. Classification of model outputs for ecosystem services assessment

Finally, the process model-based simulations for different environmental interactions were used to determine the indicators for ecosystem services (ES) for fishpond aquaculture.

It is often observed that in the case of freshwater pond aquaculture, the ES assessments usually lack the description of the associated ecosystem functions as well as a detailed quantitative justification of the assigned values.

In order to address this challenge, we first selected ES indicators using the extensive list of indicators provided by Maes et al. (2014) as well as specific pond aquaculture related research (Hoess and Geist, 2022; Rey-Valette et al. 2024). Following the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) (Haines-Young & Potschin-Young, 2018), the selected indicators were then modified and divided into three main categories: provisioning services, regulating, and maintaining services, and cultural services. This allowed the indicators to accurately reflect the unique case of freshwater pond aquaculture. In addition, a thorough categorization of the fishpond aquaculture ES was carried out, emphasizing their grouping, class, division, and measurable indicators using model simulations. Their relationship to the appropriate model compartment, element and process was also identified. The results of the categorization of the model outputs as ecosystem services indicators is presented in Table 1. It was inferred that in addition to displaying the ES-related flows between the universe of discourse and the environment, the model's simulation also considers the ES that exists within the system boundaries itself, such as production of oxygen by the phytoplankton used by the fish in the pond; lateral transfer of nutrients between the pond and the soil, etc.

Table 1. Examples for the categorization of model environmental outputs as ecosystem services from pond-reed system

Division	Group	Class	Indicator	Model compartment	Model element/ process	Explanation
(Based on Haines-Young & Potschin-Young, 2018)						
<i>(i) Regulatory and maintenance services</i>						
Maintenance of physical, chemical, and biological conditions		Global climate regulation by reduction of greenhouse gas concentrations	Carbon sequestration	Land reed	Photosynthesis	CO ₂ sequestered from atmosphere
			Carbon storage	Pond reed		
Regulation of physical, chemical, biological conditions	Atmospheric composition and climate regulation	Regulation of temperature and humidity, including ventilation and transpiration	Local moisture recycling capacity	Land reed	Evapo-transpiration	Emission of water vapor from plant surface
				Pond reed		
				Pond	Evaporation	Movement of water from pond to air
				Soil		

Other types of regulation and maintenance service by living processes	Other	Other	Micro-scale oxygen production	Land reed + Pond reed	Photo-synthesis	O ₂ released to the air
				Soil	Respiration	
			Aquatic oxygen production	Pond	Food web primary production	O ₂ produced by eukaryotes and cyanobacteria, which is used by various aquatic organisms
Mediation of flows	Liquid flows	Hydro-logical cycle and water flow maintenance	Soil moisture	Land reed	Side flows	Moisture retention in the soil around the pond
			Water store capacity	Environment	Water storage	Water collected in the pond
Mediation of waste, toxics and other nuisances	Mediation by ecosystems	Filtration/sequestration/storage/accumulation by ecosystems	Nitrogen and phosphorus retention and removal	Pond	Detritus	Accumulation in sediment
				Land reed	Side flow	Accumulation in the soil through lateral flows
					Uptake by plant	Uptake from upper soil solution by reed plant
(ii) Provisioning services						
Material and Energy	Biomass and Biomass-based energy sources	Materials from plants and plant-based resources	Harvested reed biomass for various purposes	Environment	Product reed	Harvested photo-synthetic reed biomass
Nutrition	Biomass	Animals from in-situ aquaculture	Aquaculture production	Pond	Produced carp	Harvested carp at the end of the production season
Non-aqueous natural abiotic ecosystem outputs	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials, or energy	Mineral substances used for material purposes	Nutrient rich sediment from the pond	Pond	Sediment mass	Potential utilization of pond sediment for growing different vegetables crops etc.

The simulated quantitative outputs can also be used to determine the other categories of ES such as cultural services and habitat maintenance. This was done using 'proxy indicators' for ES, which can be easily characterized based on rule-based qualitative layers generated by the simulations of the quantitative models. These ES indicators were selected from several literature sources related to freshwater bodies, ponds, wetland etc. and were processed further. The use of these rule-based proxy indicators facilitates rapid assessment at the local level in situations where data are lacking, as the assessment of cultural ecosystem services is always laborious (Chalkiadakis et al. 2022). Few examples of such rules are illustrated below:

- The attractiveness, enjoyment and recreational aspects of ponds is closely linked to the clarity and transparency of the water. Several methods exist to measure the clarity of water, and one of the most common one among them is measuring the Secchi depth. It is a tool that is majorly influenced by factors such as phytoplankton concentration, detritus, dissolved oxygen and nitrogen and phosphorus levels (Alam et al. 2017). Using empirical relationships between Secchi depth and the parameters (Zou et al. 2020), the model constructed in the present work can be extended to predict the Secchi depth. This can be further built into a rule in the model to assess the aesthetic and recreational value of the pond:

If Secchi depth = 'range' (i.e., between 0.25 and 0.30 m (Terziyski et al. 2016)) then aesthetics = 'supported'.

Depending on the range of Secchi depths prescribed for different types of water bodies, the rule may be modified.

- In addition to providing various ecosystem services, reed vegetation surrounding ponds serves as vital habitats and safe havens for protected species of invertebrates and vertebrates, thereby contributing to habitat maintenance for biodiversity. Simultaneously, denser reed growth sustains populations for recreational activities such as birdwatching, fishing, and other nature-related experiences. Reed beds contribute to diverse landscape patterns and enhance the visual appeal of the pond area (Bekefi & Varadi 2007, Sharma et al. 2023). Consequently, a rule was devised which can be further integrated into the model to evaluate these functions:

If 'pond_reed' and 'terrestrial_reed' = 'large_amount' (e.g., 30% of pond area and terrestrial reed density > 100 plants/m²) then habitat_conservation = 'supported' and aesthetics = 'supported' and recreation = 'supported'.

- In numerous regions across Europe, it remains customary to collect the reed plant for crafting purposes and construction materials, including panels, mats, fencing, insulation, and roofing (Köbbing et al. 2013). This practice of harvesting reed during winter adds to the cultural legacy of the region, consequently enhancing its appeal to tourists. This can be accounted as a proxy indicator for cultural heritage. An illustration of the model rule that can be embedded to evaluate these aspects is outlined as follows:

if reed_for_use = 'large_amount' (e.g., reed cover in pond > 20% and harvesting 75% or more) then thatched_houses = 'many' (e.g., between 10-20) and compostable_used_roof = 'yes' (i.e., nitrogen and phosphorous return to soil) and heritage = 'supported' and aesthetics = 'supported' and recreation = 'supported'.

5. Monetary valuation of ecosystem services from fishpond aquaculture

To carry out the monetary valuation, a combination of different economic valuation methods for ES was used.

Carbon storage: In the aquatic systems, carbon dioxide fixation service is majorly provided by the macrophyte reed vegetation. The carbon sequestration rate of 29.93 t/ha/year (for annual above-ground biomass (AGB)) resulting from the model simulations and the social cost of carbon of EUR 50.44 per tonne of CO₂e (for 2024) (OECD, 2024) were applied. Various literature sources (Edit et al., 2020) for plants in a wetland habitat type suggest that the ratio of above-ground carbon (e.g., vegetation) to below-ground carbon (e.g., roots, soil organic carbon) to be 10:1. Accordingly the carbon stored by below ground biomass (BGB) of reed plants was also calculated.

Oxygen production: The reed vegetation in and around the fishponds contributes to the local level oxygen production as well, thus playing an important role in improving personal health. Thus, to evaluate the relative cost of oxygen produced by the reed areas (maintenance free) we adopted a replacement/alternative cost method. According to multiple web sources the price of clear O₂ for breathing purposes is around 0.8 EUR/litre. Cheaper options are available for hospitals etc but they require high maintenance thereby enhancing the overall costs. The model outputs revealed that the O₂ is produced at the rate of 8.6 kg/ha/day by reed plants and 6.4 kg/ha/day by the soil, thus, accordingly the annual amount was calculated. Considering the density of O₂ gas at standard temperature and pressure (STP) (0°C, 1 atm), the total amount of O₂ (in kg) as model output was then converted to litres.

Nutrient retention: Fishpond systems have been shown to retain nitrogen and phosphorus in the pond water from fertiliser, feed, inlet water and stocked fish. The amount of nitrogen and phosphorus retained by our example fishpond system is shown in Table 2. According to a study by Roy et al., 2023 the cost of removing 1 kg N or P from wastewater (freshwater origin) with current state-of-the-art effluent / wastewater technologies is between 3-5 € kg⁻¹ N removed and 19-35 € kg⁻¹ P. The economic value was estimated by multiplying these costs by the calculated nutrient retention values.

Cooling effect/micro-climate regulation: The water surface area of the fish pond systems as well as the plant evapotranspiration significantly contribute to decrease in the air temperature, especially during the summer months. The calculation for the cooling effects using the evapotranspiration rates from the model was done using the method suggested by Zhang et al., 2017. The heat absorbed by the pond is calculated as shown in Eq. (1).

$$W_h = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i * A_i * ET * \delta \quad (1)$$

Where, W_h is the heat absorbed by a wetland in summer (kJ/year); λ_i and is the water surface ratio of the i th wetland patch (%); A_i is the area of the wetland patch (m²); ET indicates water surface evaporation from June to August (kg/m²/year); δ is the heat of evaporation (kJ/kg).

The next step was to determine the economic value V_t (EUR) of the cooling effect using the replacement cost method, considering the current price of electricity (i.e., EUR 0.1 per kWh in Hungary for 2024) if the ponds were replaced by air conditioning systems. The calculations are performed based on the Eq. (2).

$$V_t = \sum_{i=1}^n W_h * P_c * \eta \quad (2)$$

Where, p_c is the electricity fee in Hungary (EUR/kWh); η is the transformation coefficient between electrical energy and heat (2.778×10^{-4}).

Water storage: Assessing the usefulness of fishponds for water management is challenging because the water requirements for these systems may conflict with water requirements for alternative uses such as drinking, agricultural irrigation, etc. On the other hand, fishponds can be seen as an alternative to ‘water retention systems’ or ‘peak flow control structures’. In this case, their hydrological benefits can be assessed using the substitution method, which is based on the cost of alternative resources. According to Turkowski 2011, the cost of constructing a retention basin reach as high as 4.2 million euro per 1 million m^3 of water storage capacity. Also reports the value stormwater protection by fishponds to be 3994 EUR/ha/year (as in 2019). Using the benefit transfer valuation approach, we adopted this value for our case and the original monetary value was adjusted to the current year using the Consumer Price Index (CPI) suggested by the World Bank.

Habitat maintenance: In terms of providing habitat for biodiversity, fishpond systems function similarly to wetlands. However, the type of fishpond management, either semi-intensive or intensive practices, can influence these aspects (Broyer & Curtet, 2012). To estimate this non-use value of habitat maintenance, we used the method proposed by Zhang et al. (2017), which mainly rely on the habitat quality index of the wetland. According to their field study, for ponds, the wetland type index, species richness index and wetland origin index were reported as 0.4 (pond wetland), 0.2 (less) and 0.8 (man-made), respectively. These normalised values are reported relative to the naturally occurring high-density marsh type, which has an index of 1. Furthermore, in their investigation Turkowski 2011, assessed the total value of services provided by fish ponds to sustain the biodiversity and creating wildlife habitats to be 395 EUR/ha/year (as in 1997). Therefore, in order to calculate the monetary value for fishponds in our case study, we first use Eq. (3) to determine the pond habitat quality index (W_q).

$$W_q = \sum_{i=1}^n 0.5 * W_{ti} + 0.3 * W_{bi} + 0.2 * W_{oi} \quad (3)$$

where W_{ti} , W_{bi} , and W_{oi} are the parameters of wetland type, species, and origin, respectively.

In the next step, monetary value of pond habitat maintenance (V_b) in EUR/ha/year was calculated using the following Eq. (4).

$$V_b = \sum_{i=1}^n W_q * V_o \quad (4)$$

Where, V_o is the average non-use value of fishponds in Europe.

Fish production: The valuation of the fish biomass produced was based on the market price method. According to the EUMOFA case study on the price structure in the supply chain of fresh carp in Central Europe, the market price of carp can range from 2.25 EUR/kg (live fish) to 4.85 EUR/kg (for fresh fish fillets on ice) (prices as of 2015). The simulation from our model for a typical Hungarian fishpond management shows that the average yield per hectare is 1.3 tonnes. According to this available data and after converting the market price to 2023 values according to Hungary's CPI, the monetary value of the fish produced was calculated.

Reed production: The reed produced in and around the fish ponds, if harvested in time, can be used in several ways. Commercially, reed can be used as a raw material for products such as pulp, ethanol, animal feed, fibreboard, etc. and for energy generation to produce pellets, electricity, or charcoal. According to the estimates by Croon, 2014, the market value of reed based produced can range from 110 to 1040 USD/tonne (approx. 107 to 1016 EUR/tonne). In our model it was assumed that 75% of the total reed biomass in the pond and 50% of the reed biomass in the surrounding area would be cut and removed from the system. Thus, a total of 15 tonnes of reed biomass can be harvested from fishponds at the end of each production year. The total monetary value was calculated by applying the market price of reed.

Pond sediment: Fish production in ponds leads to the accumulation of sediment on the pond bottom over time. This sediment is rich in nutrients such as N, C, P, Mg, P etc. Excess sediment competes with the space for fish and further resuspension can lead to increased turbidity, decreased dissolved oxygen, and may also lead to the release of toxic gases (Drozd et al., 2020; Ma et al., 2018). Therefore, the removal of pond sediments from time to time is essential. In Hungarian fishpond management, sediment is usually removed every four to five years. For this study, we assume that the sediment is removed from the pond at the end of each year, which is quantified as 12 t/ha. For monetary valuation. Proper handling of the removed sediment is also very important to avoid nitrate contamination of groundwater and surface water. Fishpond sediments, which are rich in nutrients, are excellent fertilisers with great potential for agriculture, providing an alternative to urea (Rahman et al., 2004). To conduct the monetary valuation of fish pond sediments, we use the alternative cost method and the methodology proposed by Haque et al. (2016). First, we calculated the total amount of nitrogen per hectare present in the pond sediment, and considering that urea contains 46% of nitrogen, the equivalent amount of urea was calculated. According to the average price list of agricultural inputs in Hungary proposed by the Hungarian Central Statistical Office (KSH), the average price of urea (46.3%) in 2023 was 240,960 HUF/t (i.e., 590 EUR/tonne). On this basis, the estimated total retail price of urea (equivalent to pond sediment) was calculated.

The ecosystem service valuation highlights the significant contributions of the fishpond ecosystem in terms of regulatory, provisioning, and maintenance services. The summary of results is presented in Table 2. All values are expressed per hectare of pond area, except for habitat maintenance, which is expressed as a one-off value for the whole system. Overall, the findings underscore the multifaceted benefits of fishpond ecosystems, demonstrating their economic and ecological importance in sustaining both human and environmental well-being.

6. Conclusion and recommendations

This work focused on the development of a coupled process-based model, as well as on the process model-based assessment of the environmental impacts and ecosystem services of fishpond aquaculture. The processes of managed pond food web and reed vegetation were investigated, based on the developed model. The most significant result of the coupled model of the fishpond-reed agroecosystem was the ability to interpret the quantitative environmental interactions of fishpond aquaculture in a clear and comprehensive manner by using unified model elements and linkages that represent the physical, chemical, biological, ecological, environmental, and managerial technological processes involved. The model makes it possible to determine quantitative impacts on the environment and ecosystem services, and to analyse dynamic balances and causal relationships associated with freshwater fishpond system. The designed model also shows an insensitive behaviour towards fluctuating initial conditions, thus making it more robust and reliable for decision making. In this work the architecture of Programmable

Table 2. Monetary valuation of ecosystem services from fishponds

Ecosystem service	Indicator	Quantified output from the model	Method applied for valuation	Monetary value (EUR/ha/year)
<i>Regulatory services</i>				
Carbon storage	CO ₂ sequestered annually	29.93 t/ha/year	Market price method	4866
Cooling effect	Evapotranspiration in summer season	0.205 mm/season	Replacement cost method	3034
Oxygen production	O ₂ produced annually	5475 kg/year		3840
Water store	Storing capacity of pond	13 0000 m ³		6312
Nutrient retention	Nitrogen retained by fish, reed, and sediment	2073.53 kg/ha/year		8294
	Phosphorus retained by fish, reed, and sediment	953.47 kg/ha/year	14 302	
<i>Provisioning services</i>				
Reed production	Harvested reed vegetation at the end of the production season	15 000 kg/year	Market price method	4007
Fish production	Harvested fish vegetation at the end of the production season	1300 kg/ha/year		9915
Pond sediment	Excavated sediment mass at the end of one year	12 000 kg/ha/year		385
<i>Maintenance services</i>				
Habitat maintenance for biodiversity	Habitat quality index	0.42	Estimation	26 272 (EUR/year)

Process Structures (PPS) was used to construct the fishpond-reed agroecosystem model, which provides the freedom of easy customization, reuse, extension and coupling of different sub-models and systematic incorporation of expert reasoning. To showcase the use of model simulation to determine quantifiable ES indicators from fishpond aquaculture, the three main categories of the ES i.e., the regulatory services, the provisioning services and cultural services were selected. It was inferred that indicators for certain categories of ES could be calculated directly from the simulations, while other categories, e.g., cultural ES and habitat maintenance services for biodiversity, could be derived using rules based on quantitative simulations. In the next steps, the monetary valuation of ecosystem services was conducted which shows the importance of the system in economic terms.

As it can be difficult to assess the sometimes overlapping and sometimes conflicting ES indicators, a process model-based assessment can provide a better overview on a quantitative basis. Increased reed cover can increase CO₂ sequestration, but not always, due to plant respiration and reed decomposition. Proportional harvesting maintains water space and provides material, while composting recycles nutrients. However, burning reeds wastes biomass and increases greenhouse gas emissions. Some fish farmers leave cut reed in ponds to reduce costs, leading to excess sediment and management problems. Thus, it is recommended to follow a circular pathway in the pond management practices in connection with other land sectors to ensure the sustainability of the system and the optimum delivery of the ES. Assessments based on the model developed in this study could be used for decision support to determine the appropriate level of management, to design forecasted trails and other training and education purposes. It is important to note that due to several limitations in the model contour and unavailable data, certain factors such as fish predation by cormorants and other birds could not be included in the model. Also, the developed model in its current state is limited in terms of spatial variability but is capable of extension considering sophisticated measurements.

The categorization of ES for pond aquaculture systems as well as their assessment indicators are usually based on terrestrial ecosystems or other aquatic ecosystems and thus do not reflect the actual characteristics of the managed pond system caused by the specific biological and physio-chemical conditions. Therefore, the proposed categorization and indicators in this work contribute to filling a broader research gap. Compared to traditional cost-benefit analysis (CBA) and life-cycle assessment (LCA), process model-based extensions can provide valuable information on a wide range of ecosystem functions and services, the ability to assess multiple management and climate scenarios, and a realistic view of associated uncertainties. Such model-based assessments are also crucial to provide a sound basis for the design of policy and regulatory frameworks that encompass the fishpond aquaculture sector and promote ecological intensification practices. The accurately quantified ES could serve as a valuable input for generating additional income for farmers through payment mechanisms such as REDD+ financing, blue carbon financing, etc. This approach also supports the EU in its progress towards Food 2030 vision, as well as aligning with the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG). However, it's worth noting that there are a number of challenges associated with developing pond aquaculture through ecological intensification. These include water management related issues, strategies to manage nutrient recycling in ponds, which could hinder the accumulation of carbon sediments, and the practice of using pond sediments as fertilizer for terrestrial crops, which could inadvertently lead to greenhouse gas emissions in certain scenarios.

Although these challenges related to fishpond management couldn't be eliminated but can be minimized with sufficient scientific, technical, and financial assistance as well as institutional support. There is still a large scope for identifying and designing payment for ecosystem services (PES) mechanisms in the case of fishpond aquaculture in Europe. Specifically for case of Hungarian finfish pond aquaculture, policy framework of the European Commission assigns principal area to low trophic finfish aquaculture to achieve EU Blue Economy goals. Appropriate financial support through Commission's rural

development funds can also sustain the interest of farmer and investors in continuing the traditional fishpond farming. Considering multiple cultural heritage values associated with European pond aquaculture, recognition of these systems can also be improved by its enrolment as a part of the FAO Globally Important Agricultural Heritage Systems (GIAAHS) and the UNESCO Intangible Cultural Heritage System (ICHHS) (EUROFISH 2023). Finally, knowledge transfer through better communication methods is needed to motivate farmers to undertake additional activities on the fish farm in addition to fish production in order to fully utilise the ecosystem services provided by the fish farm and to supplement their income

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